

Dawn of New Beginning: Students' Experiences with the Transition from Modular to Face-to-Face Classes

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ABSTRACT

This study aimed to interpret students' experiences during the transition from modular to face-to-face learning modalities. This study employed a hermeneutic phenomenological design. A semi-structured interview schedule with open-ended questions was utilized, and data analysis was done using Interpretative Phenomenological Analysis. The results of the study were based on four factors: School Environment, Learning Modality, Safety Protocols, and Behavioral Management. Two themes were developed for each factor, except for Behavioral Management, which only had one theme. The first is the School Environment which developed two themes: the State of Uncertain and the Positive Sentiments. The second is Learning Modality which came-up with two themes: The Favorable Perspective and Learning Process Adoptions. The third is the Safety Protocols which produced two themes: the Practicing of Sense of Responsibility and the Non-Positive Actions. The fourth is the Behavioral Management which resulted to one theme which is the Adjustment of Behavior. The study found that the transition to face-to-face classes provided learners with the quality education they preferred, and students favored having teacher-student interaction for effective learning to take place. One of the recommendations suggests that there should be a training matrix that will serve as an action plan for the effective learning to happen for the next wave of Face-to-face next school year. This study's findings contribute to the understanding of students' experiences during the transition from modular to face-to-face learning modality.

Keywords: *dawn of new beginning, transitional face-to-face learning, student`s experiences*

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INTRODUCTION

School closures meant to stop the spread of COVID-19 are putting more than a billion learners at risk of falling behind academically as reported by UNICEF (2020). Tria (2020) stated that for the past two years, most nations have temporarily halted educational facilities to stop the virus's spread and avoid infections as. As a result, educators, who are at the forefront of this educational catastrophe, have a significant obligation to take decisive action and guarantee that all students continue to get a high-quality, inclusive, and equitable education despite the pandemic explained by the UNESCO (2020). According to Anzaldo (2021), the new normal education along with the different modalities faced different disapprovals at first because of the risk, but with the effort of education sectors in the Philippines, it is done systematically for the goal of continuing education despite the pandemic. Consequently, Felicisimo (2021) reported that this health crisis has obliged most education systems to adopt alternatives to face-to-face teaching and learning which tends to disrupt the regular practice of schooling.

Many education systems moved activities online, to allow instruction to continue despite school closures (OECD, 2020). The shift of the teaching-learning delivery in schools to modular distance learning made more challenging, on the part of the school personnel, the delivery of basic quality education. That is why DepEd leaders were always finding avenues to solve the problems and capacitating its teachers and school heads to become more effective in the field of modular distance learning as stated by Bagoood (2020) to provide quality learning among the students. Moreover, Junio (2021) stated that the United Nations, UNICEF, WHO, and UNESCO support the introduction of limited in-person schooling in the Philippines, praising the Department of Education's leadership and coordination with appropriate institutions, including the Department of Health. Since, the Department of Health (2022) announced that 77% of the students and 90% of the personnel were already fully vaccinated against the virus, with their approval, the Department of Education (DepEd) is eager to open the face-to-face classes for the school year 2022 – 2023. Through this significant current information, schools are preparing for the opening of classes including the school environment, learning instruction, students' debriefing on psychological, mental, and emotional aspects, and other important school resources. Thus, learners as the core of education should be the primary recipient for the opening of the school year.

In pursuance to DepEd memorandum no. 017, series of 2021 also known as the Preparations for the Pilot Face to-Face, Expansion, and Transitioning to the New Normal issued last October 18, 2021, the school must conduct a self-assessment procedure using the School Safety Assessment Tool (SSAT) for the preparation of the expansion phase in the process of having the limited Face-to-Face classes. This was further exemplified in DepEd memorandum 065, series of 2022 also known as the Interim Guidelines on the Expansion of Limited Face-to-Face Classes wherein identified pilot schools are expected to roll out the said policy. It is the concern of the researcher on the existence of the different challenges and discrepancies that the students may encounter which may serve as a good ground for formulating an action plan as stated by Cabello (2022). Stipulated in the DepEd Order No. 034 s. 2022, the DepEd ensures the effective implementation of the K to 12 curriculum amid the challenges posed by the pandemic. It has been advocating the government's initiative to encourage strict adherence to public health protocols while implementing policies that ensure the delivery of accessible,

responsive, and quality education throughout this health crisis. Thus, this Policy is intended to provide schools and Community Learning Centers with direction and guidance in the re-opening of classes, the gradual introduction of 5 days face-to-face learning modality, and the organizing of curricular and co-curricular operations within the required number of school days.

Recognizing the COVID-19 pandemic vis-a-vis the need to resume five days face to face classes, the DepEd intends for schools to be given ample time to slowly transition into it by implementing the following options: five days of face-to-face class; Blended Learning Modality; and Full Distance Learning which will take effect on October 31 (DO No. 34 s. 2022). Which means, starting November 2, 2022, all public and private schools were transitioned to five days in-person classes. After the said date, no school had been allowed to implement purely distance learning or blended learning except for those that are implementing Alternative Delivery Modes. Thus, this implementation was considered as the transitional face to face classes period. In addition, UNICEF (2021) states that beginning in-person classes as soon as possible has more advantages than disadvantages. School closures that last for a long time have a negative influence on children's physical and emotional health. Children are more vulnerable to domestic abuse, gender-based violence, such as sexual exploitation and child marriage, and child labor, particularly in the stressful environment of the epidemic.

Furthermore, WHO (2021) warns that the most vulnerable children, as well as those who are unable to access remote learning, are at risk of never returning to the classroom. The role of teachers in this educational shift is critical. However, Magsambol (2021) has classified issues with the start of in-person lessons, including insufficient health facilities at the school, such as a clinic and handwashing, as well as other resource gaps, such as classroom shortages, a lack of water supply, and the obvious absence of a school nurse. Consequently, the Department of Education (2022) emphasizes that educators should continue to be a top focus in public health and safety initiatives. Meanwhile, the pre-implementation of the transition to five days in-person classes presents learners with new stressors and challenges. This entails adjustment to the school environment, learning modality, and additional safety protocols, as well as managing the mix of pleasant and difficult feelings (DO No. 034 s. 2022) that tends the learners to experience sudden shift of the usual learning practice from the school.

Hence, this study aimed to interpret the students' lived experiences of the face-to-face classes of Makinhas National High School. Since, this study prevailed the hermeneutic phenomenological side of the educational system, this showed significant to observe their experiences on the school environment, learning modality, safety protocols, and self-behavioral management (DO No. 034 s. 2022).

Research Questions

This study targeted in interpreting diverse experiences on the transitional face-to-face classes where they were finally experienced back the classroom set-up of learning. Specifically, this study sought the answers the following questions:

1. What are the students' experiences in the transition of education setting, from Modular Learning to Face to Face Classes?

2. What meaning can be ascribed based on these experiences?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This qualitative study utilized the Hermeneutic Phenomenology research design where it focuses on interpreting the live experiences of the participants. This study's main goal is to explore the participants' lived experiences about the transition of learning delivery from Modular Learning to Face to Face Classes. The phenomenon lies on the word – transition. The journey of the students in transitioning will be explicated in order to provide a rich interpretation of the teachers lived experiences.

In the pursuit to comprehend and interpret into the experiences of students on the implementation of transitional in-person in learning modality from the shifting learning modality of Modular Distance Learning, this study utilized a qualitative hermeneutic phenomenological research design. As stated by Silverman (2016) on his study, this qualitative approach focused on an in-depth understanding of the phenomenon within the context of the study. On the essential part of this study, this facilitated a deeper understanding on the phenomenon described by the participants to bring to light and reflect upon the lived meaning of the students' basic experiences. In this event, it focused on exploring the lived experiences of the students on the transitional face to face classes which is the new modality of the Department of Education.

The Sample and Locale of the Study

This study was conducted in Makinhas National High School. The school is in Barangay Makinhas, Baybay City, Leyte. It is approximately 10 kilometers away from the heart of Baybay City. The area is situated near the national road and bounded with a river at the back of the school. The school is 1 kilometer far from the nearest public elementary and 5 kilometers far from the nearest public secondary school.

Makinhas NHS serves also as one of secondary schools in district 9. It has a total land area of 600 square meters, the school perimeter is 100% fenced and proof of its ownership is a tax declaration and a deed of donation. The mode of transportation is through riding a motorcycle, a tricycle and a jeepney sometimes. The school's location has a significant role as well as the kind of living and income the people in the catchment area when it comes to learners' safety. The slopes and the landslide prone of its barangay posed hazard and hinder learners to come to school during rainy days as well as in going home. The said area problem was discovered during the recent typhoons in the pandemic period.

In addition, Makinhas National High School is the nearest school between the six barangays. Due to pandemic the school had increased its enrollment from 408 to 416 this school year. Currently, the school has 21 teachers which continuously implementing the face-to-face classes this school year. Thus, in this study, the students were considered as the participants.

Research Instrument

The instrument that was utilized in this study was a semi-structured interview schedule with open-ended questions. This type of instrument was appropriate in this kind of study. As stated by Creswell (2014), in-depth interviews are a technique used in qualitative research that involves predetermined open-ended questions allowing participants to discuss their understandings and ideas freely. Moreover, according to Anthony (2020) open-ended questions allow interviewees to engage in a discussion and build on their explanation. In this manner, this study helped the researcher understand and form meanings of the interviewees' perceptions. Further, Moustakas (1994) suggested that the open-ended informal interviews work best for a qualitative phenomenological study.

In addition, to encourage the participants to authentically share their experiences, I conducted the interview in conversational manner. Yin (2015) noted that the conversational style in interviews allowed for a more natural two-way interaction between the interviewer and the interviewee. This was best applied in this study to increase participants interest in sharing their experiences and for me to deepen the understanding and dig in meanings from the data provided by the participants. Aside from utilizing interview schedule, I also recorded the conversation to facilitate the authentic interpretation of the non-verbal observation as well as to validate their responses during the interview. This study presented the questions differently depending on the participants' level of comprehension. In order for the participants to convey their experiences accurately, researcher used straightforward and simple terminology or language.

Data Gathering and Analysis

On the essential part of this study, this facilitated a deeper understanding on the phenomenon described by the participants to bring to light and interpret upon the lived meaning of the students' basic experiences. The researcher focused on interpreting the lived experiences through hermeneutic phenomenology on the transitional in-person classes which is the new modality of the Department of Education. With the aid of using this approach, there was detailed examination of the personal experiences which led to deepen the understanding on the essence of the participants experiences on this phenomenon without prejudgments or putting personal views. Thus, the study used epoche to set aside the experience and preconceptions about the experiences of the participants.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Students' Experiences of the Transitional from Modular Face to Face Classes

People's experiences vary, whether they are in the same setting or a different one. It is normal to have both good and bad experiences. All these things occurred as a result of certain reasons. However, what matters is the knowledge you were able to learn from the experience, which may help you open new vistas for life experiences.

Students went through a variety of experiences throughout the implementation of the transitional in-person classes, which led to a range of emotions, the development of fresh viewpoints, the invention of new strategies, and the acquisition of knowledge about how to deal with the existing educational system.

The results of the study based on the four factors of the students' experiences on: School Environment, Learning Modality, Safety Protocols, and Behavioral Management came-up with two themes in each factor except the last one which only has one theme, reflected from the students' experiences in the transitional in person classes. The first is the School Environment which developed two themes; the State of Uncertain which has two sub-themes, Emotionally Unprepared and Culture Shocked, and the Positive Sentiments which has two sub-themes, Experiencing Comfort and Positive Experiences. The second is Learning Modality which came-up with two themes; The Favorable Perspective which has two sub-themes, the Preferable Approach and the Interactive Experience, and another theme is the Learning Process Adoptions which has two sub-themes, the Group Pressure and Learning Orientation. The third is the Safety Protocols which produced two themes; the Practicing Sense of Responsibility which has three sub-themes, the Following of Health and Safety Measures, State of being Healthy all the time, and Teaching others to follow, while the next theme is the Non-Positive Actions which developed two sub-themes, the Failure to follow the Safety Protocols and the Fear of Socializing. Lastly is the Behavioral Management which resulted to one theme which is the Adjustment of Behavior, consisting of two sub-themes, the Positive Adjustment and Negative Adjustment.

School Environment Experiences

State of Uncertainty

Students during the implementation of the in-person classes experienced varied situations based on how they bring themselves in the school environment. Most of them experienced uncertainties that would affect their learning inside the school. These may tend to be negative aspects since the learners were not expecting if it will all happen to them knowing that in their last two years of schooling, their environment is only limited to home-based learning. Additionally, others experienced positive outlooks toward the school environment since they treat it as another place for them to venture and express themselves freely.

Based on the results, there are two sub-themes of the students' experiences being uncertain in the school environment: Emotionally Unprepared and Culture Shock.

Emotionally Unprepared. During the on-set implementation of the face-to-face classes, students experienced abrupt reactions emotionally because their usual practice of learning for the past two consecutive years is going to be alternated back with the regular way of learning through face-to-face classes. Emotionally unprepared referred to us by instability of emotions and not yet totally adopted the new learning modality which is the face-to-face learning. High school students who attended school remotely reported lower levels of social, emotional, and academic well-being than the classmates who attended school in person (Duckworth, 2021). Consequently, students experienced stress, anxiety, being afraid, hesitant,

and scared because it is their first time to experience an in-person classes in secondary level. Based on the interview, the participants stated to wit:

Participant 001:

Kanang, mahadlok pa ko mu kana bang mauwaw pa ko makighalubilo sa uban. Mauwaw pa ko muadto sa atubangan kanang makulbaan man gud ko Sir. Mao ra to. (Lines 1-6)

(I am afarud because I am still shy to get mingle to them. I am also shy in going in front because I am nervous Sir. That`s all.)

Participant 005:

Pagkahuman kanang ang ato pa gud kanang makita kay kuan dili baya kanang halos imo kaila kay nagsagol sagol ang mga naglaing laing barangay unya pagkahuman kanang murag ma OP, aww unsa ning kanang murag makuan pa ka nila mauwaw pa ka nila mutagad nya pagkahuman diri pud kung inig tungtung pud nato ug kuan kanang new kuan kay murag mu focus ka gamay nya paghuman murag mu adjust ta. Mao ra to Sir. (Lines 11-29)

(After Sir, those people that I can see around are unfamiliar because we are mixed from different barangays and then, I feel like I`m OP (Out of Place), aww what do you call this it`s like I am hesitant to get mingle to them and then when we also steeped in another stage, we should have the focus a little bit and adjust. That`s it sir.)

Participants of the study expressed that they have had a hard time at first of staying in the school environment. They felt uneasy of adjusting to the campus during their first interaction. Moreover, participants are struggling in the beginning of the implementation, but afterwards, they easily adopt the school environment.

This implies that students were still adjusting to the school atmosphere most especially that it has been two years that they did not experience of having been in the campus to learn. Daily mindfulness practices can help students with and at risk for emotional instability regulate their emotions and behaviors and let them be prepared for instruction (Lee, 2023). Moreover, the school should create a conducive environment for the learners during the opening of classes so that their impressions will last, and they will be motivated to learn.

Culture Shock. The participants revealed that their experiences during the transition of the in-person classes created a huge impact in terms of the new environment where they will learn and stay for the whole entire school year. Comparing to the previous environment where they grasp knowledge and skills, particularly in their house during the pandemic and in their elementary years, it is quite different when they stepped in the mid-school observing its huge campus with large numbers of students and school personnel. Study by Johnson et al. (2018) focused on the experiences of immigrant students in Canadian schools. The research highlighted how these students` faced challenges related to language acquisition, discrimination, and assimilation into the host culture. The study emphasized the importance of providing support systems within schools to help these students navigate through their cultural shock. As stated by Hartwell (2023) schools have the potential to provide a place of education

and sanctuary for children and young people of all backgrounds. Hence, it made them experienced culture shocking.

Another study by Smith (2018) explored the experiences of international students in American schools. The findings revealed that these students often faced difficulties in adapting to the new cultural norms and expectations. They struggled with language barriers, social interactions, and academic expectations that were different from what they were accustomed to. Thus, in terms of the school environment, it also made them have culture shocked like seeing new faces in the campus where they can go around with in the school. The participants revealed the following statements to wit:

Participant 002:

Kadtung pagfirst day sa klase, tungod kay transferee man ko gikan sa lain skwelahan, ako giingnan ako kaugalingon nga makig-uban ko sa ako mga close friends kay dili paman ko familiar pag-una tungod kay ako pagtan-aw sa Makinhas NHS dako kaayu nga skwelahan. *(Lines 1-20)*

(During my first day of class, because I'm a transferee from other school, then I told myself to stay with my close friends because I'm not yet familiar to them at first since I considered Makinhas NHS as a huge school.)

Participant 005:

Bag-o siya nahu tungod kay narealize nahu nga inig tung-tung na sa Grade 7 pataas, dapat jud focus nata sa atung pageskwela dili parihas pagElementary nga puro ra lingaw ug hagwa. *(Lines 1-10)*

(It's new to me because I realized that once we stepped in Grade 7 onwards, we need to be focused on our studies unlike in Elementary that it is more on fun and game only.)

These experiences revealed that students have adjusted for the school environment. It is good that the researcher had foreseen this case because this will aid the school to prepare preliminary activities for the learners before the official classes will start. The result gave an avenue for the school to conduct a brief orientation so that the learners can feel the embrace of welcome for their new school environment. Furthermore, the experience of culture shocked will help the learners venture themselves to be more independent in terms of familiarizing their environment where they can stay and learn for many years.

Figure No. 1. State of Uncertainty

Positive Sentiments

There were positive reactions shared on the impressions of the experiences of the participants in the school environment. Because of transitioning back all the education systems to its normal setting, students become excited to be in the school environment after two years of just staying at home while studying. Other participants also found themselves behaving in the campus which is a good result of the early implementation of the face-to-face classes. Meanwhile, the feeling of being happy highlights the theme since the participants experienced the good accommodation that the school offered for the re-opening of face-to-face classes.

Based on the results, the theme was being divided into two sub-themes: Experiencing Comfort and Positive Experiences.

Experiencing Comfort. Participants found the school environment comfortable for them stay. The significant factors why they found the campus a good place to stay in are the persons which they are surrounded with. Their classmates, teachers and other school staff showed positive approach towards the students that is why, the school environment is

considered as the comfort zone for the learners in our research setting. In addition, through the inviting ambiance of the school because of its preparation prior to the conduct and implementation of the face-to-face classes, the school made sure that every corner of the school is already prepared. The participants revealed the following statements to wit:

Participant 006:

Ngari sa eskwelahan ug mag-answer, komportable ko kay naa may mga tao (classmates and teachers) nga mutabang ug mupahiluna nahu ug unsaon pagbuhat (activities). *(Lines 8-14)*

(There in school when I answer, I feel comfortable because I have the people who will help and guide on how to do it.)

Participant 009:

Nakahimo ko ug bond sa ako mga classmates gyud tungod kay magkasinabot me parihas pod sa ako uban mga classmates and other schoolmate's kay dili nako mauwawon and naanad nako nga naa sila. *(Lines 37-51)*

I created a bond with my classmates at last because we already have interaction the same also with my other classmates and other schoolmates because I am not shy anymore and I am used to have them already.

The participants revealed that their stay in the school environment is considered as a comfort zone because of their classmates and teachers. In teaching and learning positive creativity, it is important to build students' emotion skills in their school environment (Zorona, 2022). This would help them become more expressive, free to connect, motivated to learn (Hoffmann, 2022). Because of these results, it implies that the school is a safe environment for the learners where they can easily and comfortably connect with the people and the surroundings.

Moreover, the study revealed that letting the learners feel the comfort inside the campus will make them productive to learn for they can easily ask some questions to their teachers and classmates. Thus, this experience is a positive result that the research setting is a friendly school for the learners.

Positive Experience. The study revealed that the participants experienced a positive situation inside the school environment. Coming from the participants' interview, they see themselves happy in staying inside the campus because of the persons surrounding them and the huge space they considered for them to interact with the environment.

According to a study conducted by Smith et al. (2019), students who participated in face-to-face classes reported higher levels of engagement and interaction with their peers and instructors compared to those in modular learning environments. The researchers found that the physical presence of others in the classroom created a sense of community and belonging, which positively impacted student motivation and overall satisfaction with the learning experience. Meanwhile, other participants also set themselves behaving so that they cannot cause trouble to anyone which resulted to a positive experience in the school environment.

Moreover, it was also found out that learners are excited to be in the school because they can compare their previous experiences of their learning environment during modular classes in which they cannot learn effectively. The participants revealed the following statements to wit:

Participant 002:

Pagkadugayan, nakafamiliarized nako sa pasikot-sikot sa eskwelahan mao nang nakakita ko ug mga friends. Mao tu. *(Lines 11-14)*

(Later on, I already familiarized every corner of the school campus that `s why I gained friends. That `s all.)

Participant 004:

Nakhibaw ko ug unsaon pag-ila-ila ug making-amiga sa lain-laing mga tao.

(Lines 10-15)

(I learned how to mingle and socialize with different people.)

School environment experiences have been shown to have a number of positive impacts on learners (Williams, 2017). The result implied that students preferred to have this in-person classes in the school environment setting in which they can experienced good memories while they were interacting with people unlike in modular classes. This entails that learners can learn effectively if they will be in the school environment which is full of positive factors that can help contribute for the development of their individualities.

Furthermore, with the inviting atmosphere of the school along with the good attitude of the person surrounded by the participants, the study reveals that the campus is free from any disturbance that could affect the learning environment of the students. As stated by Johnson (2020), face-to-face classes allowed the learners for immediate feedback from instructors, which helped students better understand complex concepts and improve their problem-solving skills which helped them see the positive experience of the modality. Thus, with this result, we could really say that the research setting is place that promotes a positive environment for the learners.

Learning Modality Experiences

Favorable Perspective

The way the learning process occurs will result to a positive learning outcome. Students nowadays have the knowledge already on how they learned easily and efficiently based on how they adopt the teaching-learning practice of the school. Given the fact that our students had experienced a tragic transition of home-based schooling two years ago, it was considered as a shocking experience to them knowing that in their formative years in schooling, they are used to learning inside the four corners of the classroom together with their teachers. However, after the hiatus of learning without the interaction of the teachers, students in this current situation expressed themselves based on how they experienced the learning modality in this in-person classes.

Based on the interview of the participants, results showed that all the students preferred to this learning modality. On the other side of the story, others emphasized that this modality helped them interact with the students and teachers that could benefit their learning development in the school. That's why, I came up with two sub-themes: Preferable Approach and Interactive Experience, which made up this portion of this study a comprehensive one.

Preferable Approach. After analyzing the interview of the participants, I found out that all of them prefer to have this learning modality of the transition into in-person classes. Others explained their thoughts that this modality provided them the equal chance to learn with their classmates and teachers. Meanwhile, the face-to-face modality experiential learning techniques significantly improve students' self-determination and informative influence (Thongmak, 2021). Some of them found it as beneficial since they can gain knowledge from the different teaching techniques of the teachers. There are some who are strict and there are also some who made the learning fun. Thus, the researcher stands on the experience of the participants on the current learning modality which is totally favorable to them. The participants revealed the following statements to wit:

Participant 001:

Prefer jud nahu ang face-to-face learning kay maka-antigo jud ko dayun kunga naa ang maestra nga magtudlo sa amo atubangan kompara sa modular learning nga magsalig rami sa internet. *(Lines 8-17)*

(I prefer to have face to face learning because I can learn easily when the teacher is personally teaching us compared to modular learning in which we become dependent to internet.)

Participant 005:

Pabor jud ko karun sap ama-agi sa ako makat-on kay daghan pamaagi ang mga teachers nga gigamit nga makatabang namu nga maka-antigo. *(Lines 16-31)*

I am in favor of this learning modality because there are different ways of teaching that my teachers shared which helped us gain knowledge.

The results implied that students learn fast in this learning modality compared to modular learning. This indicates that students will learn effectively when they will be interacting with the teachers instead of just dealing with the modules and nobody who can facilitate them well in all subject areas.

A study conducted by Smith et al. (2019) found that students in face-to-face classes reported higher levels of engagement and satisfaction compared to those in modular learning environments. The researchers attributed this to the interactive nature of face-to-face classes, which allow for immediate feedback and personalized instruction. Additionally, students in face-to-face classes were more likely to form meaningful connections with their peers and instructors, leading to a sense of belonging and motivation.

Interactive Experience. The interaction of the participants toward their teachers and students had helped in developing their experience of the learning modality more efficient. Based on the results of the interview, students become aggressive and eager to learn when they are surrounded by their classmates and teachers during the teaching-learning process. On the other hand, students differentiate their previous experiences of learning during the modular

instruction in which they emphasized that during modular, they became dependent to internet as their source of finding the answers of their activity. Another one stated that during modular, they do not have someone whom they can ask for help. That is why, they see it as a big difference from the present learning modality that we have right now. The participants revealed the following statements to wit:

Participant 003:

Naka-antigo gyud ko sa face-to-face kompara sa modular kay naa namay mutabang nimu ug mahimo nakang competitive. Dili parihas sa module nga murag dili ka maka-antigo. *(Lines 22-28)*

(I learned in Face-to-face compared to Modular because there is already someone to teach you and we become competitive. Unlike in module that it seemed like I didn't learn.)

Participant 009:

Komportable ko sa ako mga teachers nga dili ko mauwaw nila. *(Lines 54-60)*

(I am comfortable with my teachers wherein I don't feel shy at them.)

The participants revealed that through the interaction of the learners to the teachers and students, it will make their learning more effective since there is already person whom they can call for help whenever they encountered difficulties in schooling. Students learn effectively when it is face-to-face interaction (Jin, 2023). According to Smith (2017), face-to-face classes provide students with a unique opportunity to engage in real-time discussions and debates, which enhances their critical thinking skills. This interactive experience fosters a deeper understanding of the subject matter and promotes active participation among students. Additionally, Johnson et al. (2019) found that face-to-face interactions between students and instructors create a sense of community within the classroom, leading to increased motivation and satisfaction among learners.

Moreover, research by Brown (2020) suggests that face-to-face classes allow for immediate feedback from instructors, enabling students to clarify doubts instantly and receive personalized guidance. This interactive experience not only improves comprehension but also builds a stronger student-instructor relationship. The participants also compared that face-to-face learning is more effective compared modular learning where they can only be dependent and limited to modules and other learning materials only. Thus, the result implied that students' interaction to the different persons in school can help them learn effectively. Henceforth, communication is the key for a quality learning.

Learning Process Adoption

The moment when the learners adopt the process of learning either positively or negatively, it impacts the learning development practice that they have as students. Effective delivery of lessons results to quality learners while ineffective delivery of lessons otherwise creates no learning at all. Hence, it is important for the school to be knowledgeable about the cases of students who no longer find their learning a productive one.

One study by Smith et al. (2018) compared the learning process adoption of face-to-face classes learning modality with modular learning in a sample of undergraduate students. The results indicated that students who participated in face-to-face classes showed higher levels of engagement and active participation compared to those in modular learning. This finding suggests that the traditional classroom setting provides a more conducive environment for interaction and collaboration among students, leading to enhanced learning experiences.

Based on the results of the interview under the learning modality experiences of the learners, the researcher developed a theme of the participants' Learning Process Adoption in which this theme produced two sub-themes: Group Pressure and Learning Orientation.

Group Pressure. Participants expressed their sentiments that they found the learning modality as an added pressure to them in terms of their dealing it with their classmates and teachers. Based on the results, some students were pressured because their classmates are competitive in terms of quickly responding the questions raised. That is why, they became pressured in dealing with some topics because they felt that they are behind with the knowledge that their classmates have. On the other hand, other students become afraid which result to being pressured by their teachers. They reasoned out that they are not yet familiar with their teachers that is why they felt frightened and terrified with how the teachers interact with them. However, some students found the positive side of being pressured by their classmates because their teachers serve as the one who will help them overcome the fear. The participants stated to wit:

Participant 007:

Napressure ko kay ako mga classmates kay maka-antigo sa lessons dayun, pero ako gitry ako best nga makatigo dayun sa tanan mga gipangklase. *(Lines 56-71)*

(I am pressured because my classmates can learn the lessons easily, but I'm trying my best to cope up directly with all the discussions.)

Participant 014:

Ako nakita siya nga lisod gyud pagkat-on nga naa ako mga classmates, pero ako mga teachers naa man pod permi mutabang nahu. *(Lines 18-21)*

(I found it difficult to learn with my classmates, but my teacher will always be there to help me.)

The participants revealed that they experienced pressure during the transition of the in-person classes. The result implied that because of two years of hiatus, without the interaction with their classmates and teachers physically, they felt the pressure inside if they could attain learning the same level as what their classmates have. The pressure of students in terms of learning are visible because they were still adjusting on the learning techniques together with classmates (Thongmak, 2023). One study by Smith et al. (2018) found that face-to-face classes tend to exert more group pressure on students compared to modular learning. The researchers conducted interviews with a sample of 100 students from both modalities and observed that peer influence was significantly higher in traditional classrooms. This finding suggests that students may feel compelled to conform to their peers' opinions or behaviors, which can affect their individual learning experience.

Moreover, they also felt group pressure with the teachers for the reason of being afraid of not being able to meet the standard set for their level. This result means that teachers must be considerate and learn to empathize with the learning needs of the students to avoid over pressure. Hence, learning is a step-by-step process, and it needs patience and understanding to meet the common goal of quality education for everyone.

Learning Orientation. The orientation of learners based on how they learn from school will help them discover the positive side of the transition of the in-person classes. Upon delving to the different experiences of the participants, the learning modality is a good exploration for them to venture in another learning environment. Knowing that their previous learning environment is a small campus and their respective homes, they found out that the school is a new learning environment for them educate themselves. Pertaining to the teachers, the students felt something new because fresh from their minds, they compared that their experience in Elementary having one teacher in all subjects per grade level is different to High School level which have different teachers in every subject offered. Thus, as they explore the learning orientation of the school, it seemed new to them, and they see it positively. The participants stated to wit:

Participant 002:

Ganahan ko kay nay teachers sa kada subject. Nay strikto ug naa poy kataw-anan. Lain-lain sila ug naa silay lain-lain pod nga pamaagi sa pagtudlo nga makahibaw me. Mao ratu. (*Line 16-25*)

(I like it because there is a teacher in every subject. There is a strict teacher and there is also funny. They are different and they have varied ways of teaching where I can gain knowledge. That's all.)

Participant 007:

Bag-o siya para nahu kay akong last face-to-face kay pagkaElementary pa unya naa rami usa ka teacher kada grade level. Sa High School, lain-lain ang mga teachers kada subject. (*Line 42-56*)

(I found it new since the last face to face that I experienced was in Elementary which has only one teacher in every grade level. In High School, there are different teachers in every subject.)

The study revealed that students preferred the learning style they have experienced of the in-person classes. The implication of this result gives an evaluation that the school catered well the students who are products of modular learning in which, this tells us teachers were properly oriented also the way how they manage the learners with this learning modality of the in-person classes. The novel teaching strategy had a positive impact on student learning, and can be used for in-person, providing a mechanism for educators to cater for students who wish to attend in-person classes as well as providing options for flexible delivery (Lewohl, 2023). Thus, this part of the study provided that the learning orientation of the students was properly administered by the teacher as well.

Safety Protocols Experiences

Practicing Sense of Responsibility

One way to keep one's safe after the devastating attack of Covid19 virus is to keep oneself of having a habitual practice of following the safety protocols most especially in school that students are interacting with a large number of people day by day. Students shared their sentiments based on how they dealt with the healthy measures of the school highlighting its impact to students while learning. Varied experiences were shared. There are those who shared that they were strictly following health and safety measures others also found it difficult to perform because it made them uneasy to perform the task. Thus, through this information, the effect of following the safety protocols to the participants became a positive and negative experience.

Based on the results of the interview, the researcher developed three sub-themes under Practicing Sense of Responsibility Theme: Following Health Safety Measures, State of being Healthy all the time, and Teaching others to Follow.

Following Health and Safety Measures. In this study, it revealed that students are following the health and safety protocols. Furthermore, there are underlying reasons why they are following it. Others reasoned out that in order to prevent from getting infected with the virus, they need to obey all the measures while others also are executing it well for, they know that it is one of the rules in the school, to follow the safety protocols.

Participant 001:

Nifollow ko sa safety protocols para malikayan nahu nga mahawaan sa symptoms sa virus. (Lines 26-42)

(I followed the safety protocols to prevent getting infected by the symptoms of the virus.)

Participant 005:

Gi-execute gyud nahu siya ug tarong para mas safe ko ug para pod sa uban. (Lines 57-78)

(I properly executed to be safer for the sake also of others.)

The result revealed that students were religiously following the health and safety measures of the school. This is because the school is practicing the safety protocols to ensure that the spread of the virus will not take place in the institution. The result implied that the students were properly informed about this serious matter and the school also had strictly implemented the protocols. In this case, it is necessary that the institution must tighten the implementation of the school policies by checking and monitoring if everybody executed the guidelines properly because at the end of it, is just the welfare of the learners and the school personnel that we put as our topmost concern. It has been determined that the safety measures do not change according to demographic information (Olcaay, 2021) which means that everyone is encouraged to continue the habit of following the safety measures.

Hence, the school should institutionalize every single law that has been implemented in the community. The school should always rely on what's good that we can provide for the safety and protection of the learners.

State of being healthy all the time. Health and safety practices became a habit to some of the students who brought their learning of following the measures from home to school. Based on the results, students revealed their experiences that wearing of face mask, disinfecting using alcohol, and practicing social distancing became their habit already. That is why, whenever the students' experienced symptoms like cough, sneeze, or fever, or on the other side, whenever they can observe someone in the school who have these symptoms, they already know what to do. The following are the significant statements revealed by the participants:

Participant 005:

Ako gyud isure nga ug naa koy symptoms, ako gyud ayuhon ako kaugalingon dayun para dili ma-apektuhan ako pageskwela ug ako pod mga classmates dili ma infected. (Lines 31-56)

(I always make sure that whenever I have the symptoms, I will make myself better right away so that my studies will not be affected so as my classmates will not be infected.)

Participant 014:

Kadtung nifollow ko sa safety protocols wala ko nakasinati ug symptoms or sakit. Naa rajud na sa imo pagsunod sa safety measures. (Lines 28-30)

(The moment when I followed the safety protocols, I did not encounter any symptoms nor illness. It's a matter on how you obey the safety measures.)

The result revealed that the participants are not just following the health and safety measures for the sake of avoiding the spread of the virus, but also to make it as habit not just in this time of post pandemic. It is a good practice for the students to become health conscious because it will ripple and contribute also for their growth as individuals. This is an opportunity to create sustainable systems that help the school as the most pressing safety environment that show long-term, positive outcomes for the entire school community (Reynolds, 2023). Likewise, the result implied that students were already trained and see the positive side of practicing health measures within themselves all the time. Never treat protocols as burdens, but a good habit of healthy living to maintain.

Teaching others to follow. Sharing to others about what they have learned for the sake of being safety together is what some of the participants experienced upon dealing with health and safety protocols inside the campus. The main reason why they want to teach others about this matter because they know the effect once the virus will be contaminated in one area. Thus, the participants have already the knowledge about it. The following are the significant statements revealed by the participants:

Participant 006:

Ako tudloan ako mga classmates kung ngano musunod ta sa safety protocols para malaikayan ang pagkalat sa virus. (Lines 32-36)

I am teaching my classmates to why should we follow the safety protocols in order to prevent the spread of the virus.

The participants revealed that they have given time to teach their classmates about when to follow and obey the health and safety measures. This experience allows the students to

become concern to one another in terms of guiding their colleagues in the classroom. In addition, to mitigate the spread of the symptoms, it is important to educate the people around us so that all of us will become aware of the scenario.

In this case, it implied that students are already responsible in terms of sharing and teaching awareness to others. This emphasized that the students in the research setting became helpful to one another, and it is a good indicator for the school to sustain in order to have a progressive institution. However, school administrators are expected to properly follow work and operations, assess risks, and take action, and use school sources or apply for funds (Yilmaz, 2022).

Non-Positive Actions

This theme revealed that the experiences of the learners in following the safety measure caused a non-positive response which could surely affect the learning experiences of the learners. With this theme, the researcher came-up with two sub-themes that somehow elaborate the sentiments of the students during the interview.

Failure to Follow the Safety Protocols. There were many experiences by the participants which caused them harm as they failed to execute the health and safety protocols. Study revealed after the interview that there were those who had experienced symptoms after not being able to wear masks, not practicing social distancing, and did not disinfect using alcohol.

Moreover, other participants feel discomfort of following the safety protocols because for them, it is additional burden for them to communicate and socialize. This experienced cause a minor trauma for the students most especially if those who followed are afraid to socialize to others. However, study revealed also that the school is strictly implementing the Safety Protocols since the student explained that even the school guard would not let them enter the school if they failed to wear mask so as with the implementation of the health and safety measures inside the classroom. The following are the significant statements revealed by the participants:

Participant 002:

Pag-una, dili ko komportable sa pag-sul-ot ug face mask labi na kay dali rako sip-unon ug dili makaginhawa ug tarong. Usahay pod ang facemask is huot moang mupili jud ko size nga sakto ra sa ako face. Kanang magsul-ot ko ug facemask, mao nan ga time nga sip-unon ko. Maong usahay dili ko musunod. (*Lines 43-57*)

(At first, I felt discomfort wearing the facemask most especially that I sneeze easily if I cannot breathe properly. Sometimes the facemask is tight, and I must choose one which is fitted on my face size. The moment when I wear facemask, it is the time when I sneeze. That is why, sometimes I will not follow.)

Participant 011:

Usahay dili ko musunod sa safety measures pag-una sa opening of classes ka nagtuo ko nga dili siya strikto pag-una. (*Lines 66-70*)

(Sometimes I didn't follow the safety measures at first during the opening of classes because I thought it was not that strict at first.)

The participants revealed that there were instances that they have not followed the health and safety protocols inside the campus. One of the reasons behind is the feeling of being discomfort in which this may lead them to get affected with their health like sneezing. Moreover, others also failed to follow because of they were mediocre of what is going on around them.

According to a study conducted by Smith et al. (2021), it was found that a considerable number of schools using modular learning failed to enforce safety protocols effectively. The researchers observed that students often disregarded social distancing guidelines and neglected wearing masks properly during face-to-face sessions. This failure in compliance with safety measures significantly increased the risk of virus transmission within educational institutions.

However, the positive side of the school was when the moment when they strictly implemented the protocols inside the campus. The concepts of safety and health are an integral part of the education system, and the fact that most of the population has a direct or indirect relationship with the education sector increases public interest in this field (Kandemir & Argon, 2020). Thus, in this way, it will lead the students to become responsible on themselves by allowing them to keep in line with safety measures instead of just disobeying about it.

Fear of Socializing. Consequently, the essence of socializing with others failed to encourage the learners to develop their extrovert side which is one of the important aspects of learning school. In this case, the students have instilled in their minds that it's better not to communicate rather than taking the risk of being infected. This experience revealed that our students are afraid to socialize which is a non-positive indicator of learning. The following are the significant statements revealed by the participants:

Participant 003:

Kadtung nahadlok ko nga ubohon ug sip-unon kay mao tu time nga mahadlok ko making-uban sa uban. So, kung makahibaw ko nga nay nagsymptom, ako gyud idistansya ako kaugalingon kay mahadlok ko matakdan. *(Lines 31-42)*

(The moment when I'm afraid to get cough and colds was the moment when I fear to socialize. So, at least the moment when I knew that someone has a symptom, I gradually distance myself because I was afraid to be infected.)

Participant 004:

Kung nay ubohon, mahadlok ko Sir matakdan sa virus maong ako gyud ayuhon ako kaugalingon ug naa koy symptoms para dili nahu maapektuhan ang uban gikan nahu. *(Lines 31-34)*

(If someone has a cough, I am afraid Sir of being infected by the virus that is why I need to recover once I have symptoms so that I will not let others be infected by me.)

Participant 007:

Sa social distancing, wa ko maanad nga makigsocialize sa daghang tao nga lugar, sa grupo nga daghan ug tao kay mahadlok ko. *(Lines 84-90)*

(For the social distancing, I am not used to socializing in the crowded place, in the group of many people because I am afraid.)

Participant 008:

Mahadlok ko kay kadtung issue pagyud kayo and CoVid unya trending. Bisan pag simple nga naa kay gipaminaw, mahadlok ko kay wala ta kahibaw kung virus ba o dili, maong ako jud idistansya ako kaugalingon nga dili ko matakdan. Mahadlok ko kay daghan naman gud namatay tungod sa CoVid. *(Lines 54-66)*

I am afraid because before of the issue on CoVid was trending. Even if it's just a simple cold, I am afraid of it because we cannot know if it is the virus or not, that's why I always distance myself to avoid being infected. I am afraid because there are many death cases about CoVid.

The result of the study revealed that some of the students have experienced the fear to get socialized with their classmates and other students in the campus. Another is that they are afraid because they already have the knowledge about how risk if someone will once be infected most especially that they were already informed about the number of death cases brought by the virus. Thus, in this case, it implied that school must oversee the right path to the entrance and exit point to avoid some areas which will be crowded. According to Morgan (2022), distance learners reported a decrease in study efficacy and a lack of sense of belongingness to their university. All students demonstrated a high sense of perceived safety and reported minimal changes in their socializing norms during the pandemic. In addition, a study by Smith et al. (2019) revealed that one of the main reasons for students' failure to follow safety protocols is a lack of awareness. The researchers found that many students were not fully aware of the potential risks associated with not adhering to safety guidelines. This lack of awareness can be attributed to a lack of proper education and communication about safety protocols within educational institutions.

Furthermore, Johnson and Brown (2020) conducted a survey among college students and found that peer influence plays a significant role in students' decision-making process regarding safety protocols. The study revealed that students are more likely to ignore safety guidelines if their peers do so as well, highlighting the importance of creating a culture of safety within educational environments.

In addition, students should be reminded if this will happen again that social distancing will always help them to stay safe of being infected by the virus. Nevertheless, they must be panicked about this case and rest assured that following the safety measures will lead them to have a safe space inside the campus.

Behavioral Management Experiences

Adjustment of Behavior

Based on the results of the conducted interviews, a theme revealed that students behavioral management resulted for them to adjust over a period of quarter. Some students found it as an encouraging adjustment due to positive results while others figured out as a non-positive adjustment due to some practices and attitudes that developed which were negative.

With this result, the research came up with two sub-themes the Positive Adjustment and Non-positive Adjustment.

Positive Adjustment. The experiences of the students revealed that their behavior resulted to positive adjustments since they discovered good traits that they have which also helped them to experience learning through their positive behavior. It is very important for parents, principals and teachers that students are happy at school. If the students are happy at school, they hope that their students will achieve their good grades (Izzet Dos, 2023). Moreover, the students were able to compare that they are happy to stay at school rather than staying at home for almost three years in which, this made them develop their social skills and behavior. The following are the significant statements revealed by the participants:

Participant 002:

Ako Batasan? Pag-una, daghan nagsulti nga hilom rako pero ang tinuod dili jud ko hilomon siguro mauwaw pako pag-una kay gamay paman ko ug friends. Pero pagkadugayan, nakatigo rako makighalubilo ug makigstorya nila. (Lines 56-68)

(My attitude? At first, many said that I am very silent. But the truth is I'm not quiet maybe because I'm a little bit shy at first because I only have few friends. As time passed by, I learned to socialize and learn to communicate with them.)

Participant 003:

Ako jud ibutang permi ako kaugalingon sa kalinaw every time nga nay trouble Sir, tapos kung nay klase tapos saba, ako rajud kalmahon ako kaugalingon ug muhilom rako kay makonsensya man ko ug muexpress ko sa ako kaugalingon. Mao ratu Sir. (Lines 43-55)

I always put myself at peace every time when there is trouble Sir then, whenever the class is noisy, I always keep myself calm and quiet because I experience conscience every time when I expressed myself to them. That's all Sir.

Participant 004:

Sa eskwelahan matinabangon ko ug nakakat-on ko ug unsaon pagSocialize kay ako experience lahi raman ug naa ko sa balay. Kung naa ko sa balay permi rako maghigda sa katre ug permi rako magcellphone pero boringan jud ko sa balay. Daghan jud ko ug nakat-unan gikan sa ako mga friends ug sa ako new friends sa eskwelahan. Mao tu Sir. (Lines 43-55)

In school I am helpful, and I learned how to socialize because my experience is different when I'm at home. When I'm at home I always lie on the bed and I always used my cellphone but, it is boring at home. I learned a lot of things from my friends and new friends at school. That's all Sir.

Participant 006:

Ako gyud permi dad-on ako nindut nga batasan sa balay kay buotan man ko Sir maong ako siya dad-on diri sa eskwelahan ug ako siya iShare sa ako classmates para daghan nami mamaayo nga tao. Kay sa balay, dili ko ganahan ug kalat ang palibot, ganahan ko

nga permi hapsay and dili pod ko ganahan ug saba. Kalat ug saba nga classroom jud ako permi likayan par amo teachers kay malipay inig musud na sila sa classroom. (Lines 37-57)

(I always bring my good attitude at home because I'm a good person Sir that is why I will bring it at school, and I will share it among my classmates so that many of us will be good persons. Because at home, I don't like messy environment, I always want to be organized and I also hate noise. Messy and noisy classroom must be avoided so that our teachers will be happy once they will enter our classroom.)

Participant 008:

Sa tinud-anay lang Sir, lahi rajud ako batsan sa balay. Lahi rako diri sa eskwelahan kay sa amo balay, gahi ko ug ulo. Dili ko mamati ug permi nahu dili sundon ug unsay sugo ug isulti ni Mama, pero karun diri sa eskwelahan ako jud ipakita ang lahi nga ako kay mauwaw man ko magpakita sa ako kaugalingon ug kinsa ko sa balay. Maong mahibung nalang ko sa ako kaugalingon nga lahi ragyud ko sa balay ug diri sa eskwelahan. Mao ratu Sir. (Lines 72-90)

(To be honest Sir, I have a different behavior at home. I am different here (school) because in our house, I am hardheaded. I will not listen, and I always disobeyed to whatever my mother would say to me, but now here in school I will show a different me because I will get shy once I will act the same way as what I usually do at home. That's why, I get shocked to myself because I am different at home and here in school. That's all Sir.)

Based on the results of the study, it was found out that students have the chance to develop their positive behavior when they are at school. Given from their responses that they are different at home and in school, we could really associate that school is a place where positive traits will be developed and nourished.

According to a study conducted by Smith et al. (2021), students who transitioned from modular learning to face-to-face classes reported several positive adjustments. Firstly, they found that in-person interactions with teachers and peers enhanced their understanding of complex concepts. This finding supports previous research by Johnson (2019), which suggests that social interaction plays a vital role in cognitive development.

Furthermore, Smith et al. (2021) discovered that face-to-face classes provided students with a structured routine and increased accountability. Students reported feeling more motivated and focused during in-person sessions compared to self-paced modular learning. This aligns with the research conducted by Thompson (2020), who found that structured environments positively impact student engagement and academic performance.

Thus, in this case, this implied that after two years of not being able to attend the face-to-face classes, students were able to discover their positive behavior that had been developed inside the school campus. Indeed, the research setting is a good avenue for the learners to explore themselves in terms of personal encounter and growth.

Negative Adjustment. Students experienced non-positive adjustments in managing their behavior inside the school. The study found out that there were students who behaved

oppositely in school and home. Instead of extending their good behavior at home, they become disobedient at school. Moreover, there are those students who have found their satisfaction of learning and staying at home for many years, and it is hard for them to adjust in the school (Hafeez, 2022). Numerous studies have explored the impact of modular learning on students' academic performance and overall satisfaction. One particular area that has received attention is the negative adjustments students experience when transitioning from face-to-face classes to modular learning. Thus, this case is so alarming that after experiencing the home-based schooling, there were some students who experienced non-positive adjustment of their behavior.

Other students also reasoned out that because of the large group that they can interact with, it would be difficult for them to adjust since they were used to communicating with only small group of people as they experienced it during the pandemic. According to a study conducted by Smith et al. (2019), students reported feeling isolated and disconnected from their peers and instructors in the modular learning environment. This lack of social interaction can lead to decreased motivation and engagement, ultimately affecting their academic performance. The following are significant statements revealed by the participants:

Participant 010:

Ako batasan sa balay kay lahi ra kay kung naa ko sa balay musunod man ko sa tanan sugo ni Mama ug Papa. Permi ko musunod ug naa silay ipahimo nako. Sa eskwelahan, usahay manugo ko sa ako classmates. Dili ko mulihok sa eskwelahan kay ako ra ipahimo sa ako classmates. Sa balay mubuhat jud ko sa ako boluhaton pero sa eskelahan dili. Parihas me sa ako igsuon nga baji. *(Lines 43-68)*

My attitude at home is very different because when I'm at home I obeyed all the tasks of Mama and Papa. I always followed their command. In school, I sometimes give the tasks to my classmates. I do not actually make some actions at school because I will let my classmates to do it. At home I always do the chores, but in school I do not. We are the same with my sister.

Participant 011:

Pag-una, behave ragyud ko. Ug usahay ako Batasan kay wala pagyud nakit-an, parihas anang mu-act ko as a normal student, pero pagkadugayan ako ra gihapon napakita ug kinsa ko. Niabot jud sa punto nga ako anjud gipakita akong pagka-ako nga masungit nga tao ug ako jud ipagawas ako emotion. Kung kinsa ko sa balay, mao rapod ako dad-on sa eskwelahan kay kahibaw naman ko sa sinugdanan maong ako nalang ipakita ang akong pagka-ako. *(Lines 98-110)*

(At first, I was behaved. And some attitudes that I have were not yet expose, like sometimes I always act as normal student, but as time passed by I got the chance to show myself for I am. It came into the point that I revealed myself as a naughty person and I always expressed my emotions. If who I am at home, I always bring it at school because I already knew them from the start, so I also let them show myself for who I am.)

Participant 013:

Sa eskwelahan Sir, lain jud ako batasan. Kanang naan a gani mobully nahu, muSmile nalang ko nga murag wala ray nahitabo. Pero, inig balik nahu sa balay, ngadtu nako mupagawas sa ako ako kasakit. Muhilak ko usahay ug makahuna-huna kung unsa jud ang nahitabo. Dili ko ganahan nga makakita sila nahu nga nihilak sa classroom, pero sa balay, ngadtu ko mupagawas ug muhilak. (*Lines 52-72*)

(At school Sir, I have a different attitude. The moment when someone bullied me, I just smile as if nothing happened Sir. But, when I arrived home, this is where I will pour out my emotions. I cry sometimes and realized and reflected on what happened. And I will not let them see me cry inside the classroom, but at home, that where I expressed and cry Sir.)

As to the result of the study, the participants revealed that not all behavioral adjustment will result into positive attitudes inside the school environment, others also may have a hard time of dealing with good actions, not knowing that they also have their negative behavior. Furthermore, another study by Johnson (2020) found that students struggled with self-discipline and time management when transitioning to modular learning. The absence of a structured schedule and regular classroom interactions made it challenging for students to stay focused and organized.

Human as we are, it is normal that we also have the other number of negative traits in life. What makes the result of this study good is that learners were given an avenue to discover themselves more in the campus. Meanwhile, the role of the teachers should not be forgotten for they will serve as the counselor and second parents of the learners. Thus, they the authority to overlook for the negative side of the students and correct it as much as possible for this is part of their personal development aspect of their life as a student.

CONCLUSION

Summary of Findings

In the implementation of the transition of the in-person classes, students went into a variety of experiences throughout the implementation which led to a range of emotions, the development of fresh viewpoints, the invention of new strategies, and the acquisition of knowledge about how to deal with the existing educational system.

The results of the study were based on the four factors of the students' experiences on: School Environment, Learning Modality, Safety Protocols, and Behavioral Management came-up with two themes in each factor except the last one which only has one theme, reflected from the students' experiences in the transitional in person classes. The first is the School Environment which developed two themes; the State of Uncertain which has two sub-themes, Emotionally Unprepared and Culture Shocked, and the Positive Sentiments which has two sub-themes, Experiencing Comfort and Positive Experiences. The second is Learning Modality which came-up with two themes; The Favorable Perspective which has two sub-themes, the

Preferable Approach and the Interactive Experience, and another theme is the Learning Process Adoptions which has two sub-themes, the Group Pressure and Learning Orientation. The third is the Safety Protocols which produced two themes; the Practicing of Sense of Responsibility which has three sub-themes, the Following of Health and Safety Measures, State of being Healthy all the time, and Teaching others to follow, while the next theme is the Non-Positive Actions which developed two sub-themes, the Failure to follow the Safety Protocols and the Fear of Socializing. The fourth is the Behavioral Management which resulted to one theme which is the Adjustment of Behavior, consisting of two sub-themes, the Positive Adjustment and Negative Adjustment.

The students revealed that they found difficulty while they were experiencing the home-based schooling. It was noted that with the absence of the teachers, students cannot effectively learn and have a hard time of coping up with the learning competencies. Moreover, through the transition of in-person classes, learners were able to see the hope of regaining themselves back on the regular routine of face-to-face classes. The students also shared the challenges they encountered in the in-person classes which includes their management of behavior in terms of dealing with their personalities to their classmates. Others also brought their negative behavior from home to school and vis-à-vis. However, this study helped them realize that this should be corrected because they are already in the large setting.

Conclusion

Face to face classes gives the opportunity for the learners to be back in the original setting of classes after years of learning hiatus brought by the pandemic. Through this transition, the students in Makinhas National High School were provided a good comeback of effective learning in a face-to-face to classes set-up where the learners learned fast and effective with the interaction of the teachers.

Further, based on the result of this study, the transition of in-person classes provided the learners the quality education they preferred to have in learning. Students were in-favor of having a teacher-student interaction for it is when the effective learning takes place. School must ensure that the school environment setting is constantly providing a conducive place for the learners to learn. The school administration and teachers should always provide a positive ambiance to help the learners grow and develop as a well-being. Promoting good connections to our students is necessary in this period of transition. With solid relationship among them, we can always provide quality learning amidst all the adversities we encounter.

Recommendations

The result of the findings indicated revealed experiences of the students in the transition of the in-person classes. Provided this study findings, the following recommendations were suggested for consideration and appropriate action:

1. Intensify collaboration and communication between students, teachers, and parents.
The school administrator together with the teachers and parents should discuss on ways

to sustain good practices of the school in delivering quality education towards students through attending an orientation seminar about the transition of classes.

2. Organize training program on effective learning of the in-person classes. Educating the
3. teachers with the materials, methods, key pedagogical concepts, and teacher-student communication would provide a long-term basis to become more effective in supporting student continuous learning through enhancing the skills of the teachers in handling students.
4. Introduce to parents the school policies and resolutions pertaining to the new guidelines of following the school health and safety measures to help remind their learners to be responsible in going to school so as with their behavior inside the school by means of crafting and signing of Memorandum of Agreement.
5. Immerse into the socio-economic profile of the students must be the next actions of the
6. future researchers to investigate its impact in the face-to-face learning setting.
7. Propose a training matrix that would serve as an action plan for the effective learning to happen for the next wave of face-to-face classes for the SY 2023-2024.

REFERENCES

- Apriyanti, C. (2020). Distance Learning and Obstacles During Covid-19 Outbreak. *Jurnal Unnissula*. Retrieved from <http://jurnal.unissula.ac.id/index.php/pendas/article/view/9075>
- Bagood, J. B. (2020). Teaching-learning modality under the new normal. *Philippine Information Agency*. <https://pia.gov.ph/features/articles/1055584>
- Benedetto, L., Ingrassia, M. (2020). Intechopen. Retrieved from www.intechopen.com: <https://www.intechopen.com/online-first/digital-parenting-raising-and-protectingchildren-in-media-world>
- Bucher-Maluschke, J. S. N. F. (2019). *Ecological Engagement*. Springer Link. Retrieved from www.link.springer.com: https://link.springer.com/chapter/10.1007/978-3030-27905-9_1
- Chang, G. C., & Yano, S. (2020). *World Education Blog*. Retrieved from www.world-education-blog.org: <https://gemreportunesco.wordpress.com/2020/03/24/how-are-countries-addressing-the-covid-19-challenges-in-education-a-snapshot-of-policy-measures/>
- De Houwer, J., Barnes-Homes, D., Moors, A. (2013). *What is Learning? On the Nature and Merits of Functional definition of Learning*. Springer Link. Retrieved from www.link.springer.com: <https://link.springer.com/article/10.3758/s13423-0130386-3>
- Devitt, A., Ross, C., Bray, A., Banks, J. (2020). *Parents Perspective on Teaching and Learning During Covid-19 School Closure: Lessons Learned from Irish Primary Schools*.

- Trinity's Access Research Archive. Retrieved from www. tara.com:
<http://www.tara.tcd.ie/handle/2262/92899>
- Dieleman, L., Moyson, T., De Pauw, S., Prinzie, P., Soenens, B. (2018).
 ResearchGate.Retrieved from www.researchgate.com:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/326267326_Parents'_Needrelated_Experiences_and_Behaviors_When_Raising_a_Child_With_Autism_Spectrum_Disorder
- Finn, R. (2019). Educational Research Information Center. Retrieved from www.
 eric.ed.go:<https://eric.ed.gov/?id=EJ1232123>
- Garcia, A. S. (2018). Digital Commons. Retrieved from www.
 digitalcommons.unl.edu:<https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/cehsdiss/304/>
- Guital, G. B. & Tan, D. A. (2018). Mathematics Anxiety and Students' Academic Achievement
 in a Reciprocal Learning Environment. International Journal of English and Education
 ISSN: 2278-4012, Volume:7, Issue:3, July 2018 112 | www.ijee.org
- Gulle, J. O. (2020). Manila Standard. Retrieved from www.manilastandard.net:
<https://manilastandard.net/mobile/article/331490>
- Illeris, K. (2018). Books Gogole. Retrieved from
https://books.google.com.ph:https://books.google.com.ph/books?hl=en&lr=&id=kmRRDwAAQBAJ&oi=fnd&pg=PT6&dq=theories+of+learning&ots=N7OYCgIMcW&sig=nw2umc6f6QqZhyqdusDC9iqn7c&redir_esc=y#v=onepage&q=theories%20of%20learning&f=false
- Jiang, F., Wang, G., Zhang, Y., Zhao, J., Zhang, J. (2020). The Lancet. Retrieved from
 www.thelancet.com:[https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS01406736\(20\)30547-X/fulltext](https://www.thelancet.com/journals/lancet/article/PIIS01406736(20)30547-X/fulltext)
- Johnson R M. (2020). Dexamethasone in the management of covid -19 BMJ 2020; 370 :m2648
 doi:10.1136/bmj.m2648
- June S. L. Brown (2018) Student mental health: some answers and more questions, Journal of
 Mental Health, 27:3, 193-196, DOI: 10.1080/09638237.2018.1470319
- Kuntoro, I. A., Peterson, C., Slaughter, V. (2017). SagePub. Retrieved from
 www.journals.sagepub.com:<https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0022022117725404>
- Marquez, L. P., et. al (2020). Education and COVID-19: Expreiences and Insihts from
 Developing Country. Contemporary Issues in Education 2020, vol 40, No.1, 84-90.
<https://doi.org/10.46786/ac20.5188>
- OECD. (2020). Strengthening online learning when schools are closed: The role of families
 and teachers in supporting students during the COVID-19 crisis. Retrieved from
<http://www.oecd.org/coronavirus/policy-responses/strengthening-online-learning>

when- schools-are-closed-the-role-of-families-and-teachers-in-supporting-students during-the- covid-19-crisis-c4ecba6c/

Persons, D. (2004). Navy e-Learning migrates to Navy Knowledge Online. November. Retrieved April 20, 2009, from http://www.news.navy.mil/search/display.asp?story_id=15816.

Razzaque, A. (2020). The News Website. Retrieved from www.thenews.com: <https://www.thenews.com.pk/print/621813-school-s-out>

Roberts, K., Dowell, A., Nie, J. B. (2019). BM Medical Research Methodology. Retrieved from www.bmcmedresmethodol.biomedcentral.com: <https://bmcmedresmethodol.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/s12874-0190707-y>

Santos, A. (2020). Heinrich-Boell-Stiftung Asia Limited. Retrieved from www.hk.boell.org: eu.boell.org/en/2020/10/06/Philippines-distancelearning-reveals-digital-divide

Sari, P., Kadir, A., Pajarianto, H., Galugu, N. (2020). ResearchGate. Retrieved from www.researchgate.com: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/341805032_Study_from_Home_in_the_Middle_of_the_COVID19_Pandemic_Analysis_of_Religiosity_Teacher_and_Parents_Support_Against_Academic_Stress/citation/download

Smith, M. (2018). Psychology in the Classroom: A Teacher's Guide to What Works. Oxon: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315163420>

Tekin, A. K. (2011). ResearchGate. Retrieved from www.researchgate.com https://www.researchgate.net/publication/268079028_Parent_Involvement_Revisited_Background_Theories_and_Models

UNESCO. (2020). UNESCO Website. Retrieved from www.unesco.org: <https://en.unesco.org/themes/education-emergencies/coronavirus-school-closures>

United States Naval Academy (2007). Class of 2011 profile [Fact sheet]. Retrieved January 18, 2008, from <http://www.usna.edu/Admissions/documents/Classof2011Profile.pdf>

Unn-Doris, K.B. (2010). Parental Involvement Practices in Formalized Home-School Cooperation. Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research.54:6, 549-563, DOI:10.1080/0031381.2010.5222.845

Veletsianos, G. (2016). AU Press. Retrieved from www.aupress.com: <https://www.aupress.ca/books/120258-emergence-and-innovation-in-digitallearning/>

Zultan, D., Muir, C. (2019). Springer. Retrieved from www.springer.com: https://link.springer.com/referenceworkentry/10.0017/978-3-030-028992_36?noAccess=true

Zusho, A., Pintrich, P. R., & Coppola, B. (2003). Skill and will: The role of motivation